

Step-by-step Solution of Applied Engineering Problems in Mathematics Courses Using STACK

Elena Safiulina¹, Oksana Labanova², Anna Šeletski³, Kristina Babenko⁴

Abstract: Solving practice-oriented problems in the mathematics course with first-year students allows them to clarify their understanding about the techniques and methods for solving problems that are needed in their professional activity as an engineer. This article presents the principles of creating tasks for solving technical problems. Tests were created as step-by-step problems using the STACK question type. The developed assignments received a positive assessment from external reviewers.

Keywords: Online tasks, tasks design, engineering learning

1 Introduction

Today, when the competition for jobs increases constantly, employers are looking to hire candidates who can demonstrate their practical skills rather than just a diploma with a list of theoretical qualifications.

One of engineering students' outcomes is the ability to apply a knowledge of mathematics and physics to solving technical problems. This criterion is in the first place at 21. century by data from Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, Inc. [ABET21]. It is customary in engineering schools to incorporate mathematical knowledge and skills into engineering education [F114]. The main content of mathematical subjects has not changed significantly. On the contrary, more applied tasks have been added [En14]

The fact that students will be working on real tasks will fortify their motivation and give a better view of the professional world. Solving practical problems in mathematics courses by first-year students allows them to clarify their ideas about the techniques and methods

¹ TTK University of Applied Sciences, Centre for Sciences, Pärnu mnt 62, 10135 Tallinn, elena.safiulina@tkk.ee

² TTK University of Applied Sciences, Centre for Sciences, Pärnu mnt 62, 10135 Tallinn, oksana.labanova@tkk.ee

³ Tallinn University, School of Digital Technologies, Narva rd 25, Tallinn, 10120, anna.seletski@tlu.ee

⁴ Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics, department, Ave. Nauki 9-a, Kharkiv, 61166, babenko.kristi@gmail.com

of solving problems that are necessary for their professional activities as an engineer.

This article presents the principles of creating multi-step test tasks for solving applied technical problems. Test tasks are created with a step-by-step solution using the STACK question type. At each step, the students can check their answers and get feedback.

2 Background

Teachers can provide opportunities for students to learn and understand mathematics concepts in various ways. Many instructional strategies exist, and several approaches may be utilised throughout any teaching and learning process. In education, the most popular is Bloom's taxonomy, which classifies thinking according to six cognitive levels of complexity: Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation. The categories are ordered from simple to complex and from concrete to abstract [B156]. As a basis for compiling teaching materials, writing research articles and texts, drafting tests and exam questions, teaching compilation and analysis of learning objectives and outcomes, enhancing students' thinking, asking questions, etc. it is recommended to use the revised Bloom taxonomy [Rü19]. This revised taxonomy consists of six major verb categories including Remember, Understand, Apply, Analyse, Evaluate, and Create. The first three categories require a good deal of involvement and scaffolding from teachers and focus on knowledge, comprehension, and application. The other three categories are more sophisticated and involve higher-order thinking by learners. These elements emphasise analysis, evaluation, and creativity [An01].

Applying this revised taxonomy to the problems solving one has two types of question: reproductive and productive. Productive questions provide students the opportunity to create, analyse or evaluate. These questions are frequently open-ended and divergent in nature. Reproductive questions prompt students to imitate, recall or apply knowledge and information taught by the teacher. Reproductive questions are typically convergent and have only one correct answer. [TGD09]. The latter type is well suited for task-based learning, which serves as means for students to build math concepts and develop skills.

3 Development of Practical Tasks of Applied Engineering Problems

Continuing the process of reforming the volume and content of mathematical subjects, which began in 2017, the teachers of the Science Center of the TTK UAN are revising and updating the materials of the courses "Applied Mathematics I" and "Applied Mathematics II" [SL20]. Following this general trend, it was decided to enrich the course materials with practical tasks using computer-aided assessment. The questions development process is conducted on nonlinear model ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation), because it represents a dynamic and flexible guideline for building effective teaching and learning tools [Br97], [SG98].

3.1 Analysis of needs for the development of practical tasks

In the first phase, interviews and peer discussions with representatives of the institutions were carried out. It was discussed which topics from the „Applied Mathematics I“ course are used in engineering courses. After clarifying the topics of the application, the curriculum of applied mathematics was analysed. As a result, the course is divided into several main topics and applied tasks contain all the educational moments of each topic (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: “Applied Mathematics I” topics division

3.2 Practical Tasks Design and Development

The concept of practice-oriented problems is done in collaboration with teachers of the TTK UAS and the Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National Economic University. These tasks are designed in such a way as to show the possibility of applying the knowledge gained while studying the topics of the „Applied Mathematics I“ course. It means that each task translates several mathematical concepts into real practice, helping students understand the impact of these topics on their future work.

Task 1. When planning the development of the new quarter of Tallinn, it is necessary to relieve the three main highways. To do this, you can install traffic lights on-demand, automatic traffic lights, or make an underpass for passengers. The average time it takes for a car to travel along each street is shown in the table (see Tab. 1). At the same time, negative values show the expected downtime in a traffic jam or at traffic lights. How many traffic lights and underpasses do you need to build?

	Underpass	Automatic traffic light	Underpass Traffic lights on demand	Maximum travel time
Street 1	2	-1	-4	4
Street 2	6	1	4	60
Street 3	6	-1	4	60

Tab. 1: Average time to travel along a street

Task 2. For the repair of one-, two- and three-room apartments in an apartment building, it is necessary to carry out painting, glass, and wallpaper work. The rates of time expenditures for each type of work are indicated in the table (see Tab. 2). How many one-, two- and three-room apartments are there in the house?

	One-room ap	Two-room ap	Three-room ap	Total time spent
Painting	4	7	10	316
Glass	12	15	17	620
Wallpaper	2	3	4	132

Tab. 2: The rates of time

Task 3. A cruise ship begins its journey from **Port 0** to its destination of **Port C** with intermediate stops over two ports: **Port A** and **Port B** (see Fig. 2). The ship sails OA km in the direction 30° to the northeast to **Port A**. From **Port A**, the ship sails AB km in the direction 15° northeast of **Port A** to **Port B**. The last leg of the cruise is BC km from **Port B** to **Port C** in the direction of 25° northwest to the north of **Port C**. Find the total distance the ship travelled from **Port 0** to **Port C**.

Fig. 2: A cruise ship trip

Task 4. The packaging company produces boxes for the logistics company X. From a square sheet with side $a = 20$ (cm), they cut out identical squares so, as to obtain boxes of maximum volume. What should be the side of the square they need to cut?

Task 5. A radius of a pneumatic cylinder of the machine equals $R = 0.1$ (m). This cylinder is filled with gas at atmospheric pressure. Find the work A (J) of the piston when moving it from 0.04 (m) into the depth of the cylinder by 0.02 (m).

The temperature does not change, and atmospheric pressure is $p = 103,3$ (kPa) (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: A pneumatic cylinder of the machine

The development phase was based on the results of the analysis and design phase. To provide a revised Bloom's taxonomy, tasks propose a specific multi-step sequence (algorithm) of actions, where each subsequent step is logically linked to the previous one. The step-by-step presentation of the solution serves another, even more, important pedagogical task: passing from one stage of the solution to the next, the student learns the material faster and better. Moreover, a detailed approach allows the authors to control the educational actions of students in the process of studying the course material: to prompt students to effective decisions, to fix their attention on certain points of the material that students usually do not notice or misunderstand.

STACK questions are used here because of the ability to ask different types of inputs in the same question (for example, when a student can enter a mathematical expression and choose true/false), versions of the questions are generated randomly in structured templates, and the ability to quickly provide feedback on every step (see Fig. 4).

Fig 4. Task 5 as a step-by-step question with STACK

Performing many versions for similar tasks on a specific topic, students are mastering an effective algorithm of actions when analysing the studied phenomena.

3.3 Practical Tasks Implementation and Evaluation

To demonstrate these exercises, they were offered to first-year graduate students at Tallinn University. These students are current or future mathematics teachers. Most of them work in schools in grades 6-9, some in grades 10-12. The implementation took place in a group of 14 people within the subject „Selected Topics in Mathematical analysis“. After the students went through the tasks, they were asked to fill out a questionnaire posted on the Internet. It consisted of 4 scaled statements and 3 open-ended questions. Although tasks were in English, the questionnaire was translated to Estonian. We wanted students to feel free to answer, especially on open questions.

At the end of the implementation phase, all data and information, which was collected through the questionnaire, were saved for analysis in the evaluation phase.

Fig. 5: Answers of the scaled questions a), b), c), d)

In the first question on the satisfaction of developed tasks about 79% of students were (extremely or very) satisfied with the step-by-step structure of tasks and only 7% were not

satisfied at all (see Fig. 5, a). The design of the tasks was also liked by more than 70% of respondents. Nobody selected the option “Not at all satisfied” (see Fig 5, b). The next item was about the difficulty of tasks. Half of the respondents said that tasks were easy or somewhat easy and 14% found tasks somewhat difficult. (Nobody selected “Very difficult”) (see Fig. 5, c). It could be caused by the student's level of knowledge. Some students come to university master level right after finishing bachelor level, but some of them finished their bachelor study many years ago. Also, this curriculum of Tallinn University does not require a bachelor's in mathematics, only some mathematics courses must be done. The last scale question was about filling the gaps with answers. 50% found it easy and 21% somewhat difficult. Nobody selects “Very difficult” (see Fig. 5, d). It is important to comment that the STACK plugin was put in Tallinn University's Moodle only one month ago, so most of the students see it for the first time.

The last three questions were open-ended. Firstly, the authors asked students to describe what they liked. Almost all the students named the structure of the tasks and guidance or step-by-step guidance. Some of them remembered instant feedback when they entered formulas. Some talked about design and auxiliary drawings. Secondly, the authors asked them to describe what they disliked. Almost half of them dislike long scrolling, they want to see tasks all the time. More skillful students said that a lot is predetermined, and they prefer to input more by themselves. Some students had difficulty entering math text. A few wanted clearer division of task parts.

The last question in this series is about the future of such kinds of questions. Respondents offer for example to make "helpful hints".

Some of them asked to add an online calculator and sketchpad, because they wanted to do all calculations in the same program, also (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Answers of the open-ended questions a), b), c)

4 Future Plans

Analysing the questionnaire answers authors decided to create short instructions about the STACK questions inputs syntax, think about how to make a student's work only computer-based (built-in online calculator, sketchpad), and develop a clearer design of questions according to the possibilities of STACK. After making necessary changes in the tasks, the authors will move to the implementation phase for the practical tasks with the target group - TTK UAS first-year students.

Bibliography

- [ABET21] ABET, Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, Inc <http://www.abet.org>, accessed: 24/05/2021
- [An01] Anderson, L. W., Krathwohl, D. R., Airasian, P. W., Cruikshank, K. A., Mayer, R. E., Pintrich, P., Wittrock, M.: A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives. New York: Longman, 20021.
- [Bl56] Bloom, B. S.: Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook I: Cognitive domain. New York: Longmans, Green, 1956.
- [Br97] Briggs, L. J.: Instructional design: Principles and applications. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Educational Technology Publications, 1997.
- [Rü19] Rütman, T.: Inseneripedagoogika. STEM valdkonna õppeainete mõjus õpetamine ja õppimine. I osa. Teine, uuendatud trükk. Tallinn: TTÜ kirjastus, Aura trükk, 2019. (in Estonian)
- [SL20] Safiulina, E.; Labanova, O.: STACK: stages of the process through the beginner's experience. 3rd International STACK Conference. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3955597, 2020.
- [SG98] Seels, B., & Glasgow, Z.: Making instructional design decisions: Merrill, 1998.
- [TGD09] Tienken, Ch. H., Goldberg, S. & Dirocco, D.: Questioning the Questions, Kappa Delta Pi Record, 46:1, 39-43, 2009.